

SIGNIFICANCE OF CURRENT REFORMS IN PREVENTION OF TRAFFIC ACCIDENT

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Annotation: This article provides statistical information about road accidents, their causes, the conditions that made them possible, as well as several suggestions for preventing road accidents.

Keywords: UNICEF, Korean experience, traffic accident, rule changes road traffic.

In our developing time, we can see that technology is becoming an integral part of our life. At this point, we should highlight the vehicles that bring our distance closer, and serve needs of people for various purposes.

However, the speed of movement of vehicles on the roads and the number of road traffic accidents have being increased, the result of traffic accidents we can see that people are injured in various degrees and to be invalid due to the injuries even losing their lives. In addition, there are some problems which are based on the field of environment and nature pollution because of the gases emitted by vehicles.

Currently, according to statistics of the World Health Organization, about 1.4 million people have become victims of road traffic accidents every year.[1] In our country more than 10,000 traffic accidents occurred in 2021. In these accidents, more than 9,000 people were injured, and about 2,500 people died, including 263 children, which is a very sad situation. [2]

During 6 months of 2022, 3 thousand 559 roads traffic accidents occurred. 2 thousand 775 people were injured in various degrees, 284 people died prematurely due to these accidents. [3].

According to statistical data show that we need to find a solution to this urgent problem by implementing reforms using modern information technologies to prevent traffic accidents.

For this purpose, by the Cabinet of Ministers on April 12, 2022. Decision No. 172 was adopted [4]. With this decision, some traffic rules were changed.

According to A.A. Nasilloev, "Biror bir davlatda qonunlar yaratilar ekan, o'sha davlatning fuqarolari, shuningdek, u yerda bo'lib turgan boshqa shaxslar uchun ushbu qonunlar ularning ma'lum bir huquqlari ta'minlanishini kafolatlash bilan birlilikda ularga burj va majburiyatlarni ham yuklaydi"[5].

In fact, according to this decision, the speed of vehicles is allowed not to exceed 70 kilometers per hour in populated areas, 30 kilometers per hour on

roads up to 300 meters around schools and preschools, and 20 kilometers per hour in residential areas and neighboring areas (on roads between residential buildings). The fact that it has demanded imposes more responsibilities and obligations on road users. In this way, it is possible to prevent traffic accidents related to the death of people, especially children, and to ensure the safety of citizens in residential areas and neighboring areas.

This change, which is being implemented in practice, is included in our legislation because the Korean experience was studied and it gave the intended result and effect.

Also, on May 13, 2022, at a press conference held in AOKA with the participation of UNICEF, the UN Economic Commission for Europe and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Ministry of Road Safety

"Measures to significantly reduce the death of children in traffic accidents" were announced.

They are:

- strengthen national legislation and policies that ensure the enforcement of laws for all road users, including teenagers and young adults;
- infrastructure and post-accident services;
- development of school territory improvement programs and a system of fines for traffic violations in the school territory;
- development and implementation of a reliable system of issuing driver's licenses to new drivers;
- development and implementation of educational programs on road safety for schoolchildren;
- development and implementation of an effective system for increasing public awareness;
- support to civil society organizations[6].

As a result of the implementation of the listed measures, safety on the roads will be ensured more effectively, we can achieve the goal of preventing people, especially children, from various degrees of physical injury, premature death, and eliminating possible negative situations as a result of road traffic accidents. Also, through legal promotion, we will convey the ongoing reforms to ensure road traffic safety to all participants of the road traffic, raise their legal consciousness and legal culture by introducing the accepted normative legal documents to our citizens, improve road infrastructures, and use modern information technologies by promoting digitization. It serves to prevent

violations that may be committed on the roads, to eliminate possible negative consequences.

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